

Metal Complexes as Ligands : Binuclear Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes with Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Bis(acetylaceton)ethylenediamine

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Using bis(acetylaceton)ethylenediamine complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} as ligands¹, bimetallic complexes of alkali and alkaline earth metal salts of inorganic and organic acids have been prepared.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing (1 h) a mixture of [Cu(acac)₂en or Ni(acac)₂en] and alkali or alkaline earth metal salts in the ratio of 1 : 1 in absolute ethanol. Dissolution took place and the adducts precipitated out. In some cases slight heating was necessary to complete the reaction.

Analytical data suggest the general formula as [M_a(acac)₂en].M_bL, where M_a = Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} and M_bL = Li, Na, K salts of inorganic and organic acids. In case of alkaline earth metals the general formula of the adducts have been established as [M_a(acac)₂en].M_b'L, where M_b'L = Ca salts of inorganic and organic acids. The characterising data are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. (°C)/(Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		N	C	H	Ni/Cu
Ni (acac) ₂ en = L (Reddish brown)	190				
L.LiCl	220 (Brown)	8.00 (8.77)	45.10 45.80	5.00 5.95	17.98 18.38)
L.KSCN	222 (Brown)	10.90 (11.11)	37.50 38.12	4.00 4.76	15.00 15.54)
L.NaSCN	228 (Brown)	11.50 (11.61)	38.50 39.81	4.00 4.97	16.00 16.23)
L.NaBr	207 (Brown)	8.01 (7.29)	36.89 37.58	4.30 4.69	14.90 15.30)
L.NaIN2N	260 (Brown)	8.10 (8.80)	54.34 55.10	4.98 5.10	11.93 12.31)

Table-1 (Contd.)

L.KIN2N	238 (Brown)	8.00 (8.54)	52.97 53.70	4.10 4.88	10.82 11.70)
L.K(Anth)	240 (Brown)	8.99 (9.21)	49.83 50.03	5.00 5.26	12.90 12.88)
L.CaCl ₂	220 (Brown)	6.62 (7.14)	35.94 36.96	4.50 4.59	14.18 14.98)
L.CaBr ₂	228 (Brown)	5.91 (5.84)	30.85 30.08	3.80 3.76	12.82 12.26)
L.Ca(ONP) ₂	230 (Yellow)	9.18 (9.38)	47.44 48.26	4.00 4.35	9.72 9.83)
Cu(acac) ₂ en = L'	131 (Purple)				
L'.NaSCN	298 (Violet)	10.92 (11.45)	42.00 42.56	4.26 4.91	16.98 17.32)
L'.LiCl	265 (Violet)	7.99 (8.64)	44.20 44.44	5.00 5.55	18.95 19.59)
L'.NaBr	265 (Violet)	6.92 (7.20)	36.23 37.06	4.00 4.63	16.00 16.34)
L'.NaClO ₄	205 (Violet)	5.99 (6.86)	35.12 35.29	4.20 4.41	15.00 15.56)
L'.Li(Anth)	215 (Violet)	9.01 (9.77)	52.90 53.06	5.00 5.58	13.83 14.80)
L'.K(ONP)	147 (Violet)	8.98 (9.08)	45.96 46.70	4.00 4.75	13.10 13.72)
L'.CaCl ₂	240 (Violet)	7.52 (7.06)	37.16 36.31	4.50 4.53	16.62 16.01)
L'.CaBr ₂	210 (Violet)	5.20 (5.79)	28.78 29.78	3.20 3.72	12.84 13.13)
L'.Ca(ONP) ₂	235 (Yellow)	9.52 (9.31)	48.76 47.88	4.60 4.32	11.38 10.55)

Infrared spectral measurements were made in nujol for the ligands and complexes between 4 000 and 600 cm⁻¹. Two possible structures for bis-acetylaceton-ethylenediamine and its divalent metal complexes have been suggested². On complexation through the partially double bonded phenolic oxygen C-O, the ν_{C-O} frequency should go up compared

to the ν_{C-O} of the 'complex ligand' $[M(acac)_2en]$. The $(C-O)$ frequency of the organic ligand $(acac)_2en$ at $1\ 143\ cm^{-1}$ (Ref. 2) showed a lower shift to $1\ 113\ cm^{-1}$ in its metal complexes, and showed almost no upward shift on adduct formation with alkali and alkaline earth metal salts. On the other hand, except in $Ca(ONP)_2.L'$, the bands at $\sim 1\ 600$ and $\sim 1\ 500\ cm^{-1}$ of the complex ligand showed a definite upward shift in the metal adducts. Either of these two bands can be due to partially double bonded $C \cdots \cdots O$.

The magnetic moment values of the alkali and alkaline earth metal adducts of $[Cu(acac)_2en]$ lie in the range 1.9–1.99 B.M. suggesting their square-planar structure. It seems that the structure of $[Cu(acac)_2en]$ remains almost same also in the isolated adducts. $[Ni(acac)_2en]$ is diamagnetic, suggesting a square-planar geometry. The binuclear complex compounds of alkali and alkaline earth metal salts with $[Ni(acac)_2en]$ are also diamagnetic except with $Ca(ONP)_2$ and $NaIN_2N$.

In the absorption spectra of the adducts derived from $[Ni(acac)_2en]$, only one band was observed

at 450–500 nm, suggesting the square-planar structure of Ni^{II} .

The metal $(acac)_2en$ complexes have been used as Lewis bases for forming adducts with alkali and alkaline earth metal salts (Lewis acids). The oxygen of metal $(acac)_2en$ are probably used as coordinating atoms.

References

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2. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 998.